

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRAKRITI, PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL AND JOB PERFORMANCE: DEVELOPMENT OF A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

AYUSHI JOSHI ¹ | JUHIE TAK ² | NEELAM KALLA ³

¹ RESEARCH SCHOLAR, UNIVERSITY – DMS, JNVU, JODHPUR.

² RESEARCH SCHOLAR, UNIVERSITY – DMS, JNVU, JODHPUR.

³ ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, UNIVERSITY – DMS, JNVU, JODHPUR.

ABSTRACT:

The psychology of a person plays a huge role in understanding his characteristics. However, the concept of Psychology is mostly studied through foreign theories. As per Ayurveda, Tridosha and Triguna, together form the Prakriti of a person. Prakriti and PsyCap are considered in the paper to study their impact on the Job Performance of individuals. Moreover, the researchers attempt to study whether PsyCap acts as a mediator between Prakriti and Job Performance.

KEYWORDS:

PRAKRITI, PSYCAP, PSYCAP, TRIDOSHA, TRIGUNA, HOPE, OPTIMISM, SELF-EFFICACY, RESILIENCE, JOB PERFORMANCE.

PAPER ACCEPTED DATE:

PAPER PUBLISHED DATE:

3rd April 2025

5th April 2025

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 PRAKRITI

Pt. Shastri & Chaturvedi, (2021) says that Ayurveda is a system of medicine that studies medical phenomena in terms of the Tridhatu Theory, also known as the three-life factor theory or Tridosha theory. The theory says that three basic elements of life help with metabolism. The three elements are Kapha, Pitta, and Vata, also known as water, fire, and air. The theory of Tridosha implies that all physiological and pathological imbalances in the human body occur due to an imbalance in the three factors of life. Like Tridosha, Triguna is also the inborn qualities of a person. While Tridosha is the qualities of a person’s body, Triguna is the integral component of a person’s mind. According to Ayurveda, nature and surrounding and every matter on earth is manifested through Prakriti. The Trigunas are Satvik, Rajasik and Tamasik guna. (“Trigunas (Sattva, Rajas, Tamas): 3 Gunas to Know Your Personality,” n.d.) <https://www.fitsri.com/yoga/trigunas>. Shilpa & Venkatesha Murthy, (2011b) mention that Tridosha and Triguna are formed of the Panch Mahabhuta (the five basic elements called Air, water, earth, ether, and fire) and impact the physiology and psychology of a person.

1.2 PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL (PSYCAP)

Fred Luthans and Youssef in their paper Investing in People for Competitive Advantage (2004) introduced the concept of PsyCap. The paper emphasized the need to focus on Human capital development for competitive advantage and found tacit knowledge, which is organization-specific and highly inimitable superior to explicit knowledge, which is imitable. One of the key

indicators for the management of human capital as introduced by Luthans and Youssef was **PsyCap**. According to **Luthans** (2007), PsyCap can be defined as “an individual’s positive psychological state of development”. The components of PsyCap are Hope, Self-Efficacy, Resilience, and Optimism.

1.3 JOB PERFORMANCE

Job performance assesses the performance of a job by an employee and checks whether the job is done well and is checked at the individual level. **Campbell** defines performance as behavior for which an individual is responsible. Here job performance is not taken as an outcome or result of the work done by an employee, as it is not only dependent on the performance but is also the outcome of various environmental factors at play, like the economic conditions, market conditions, technological advancements, government policies, etc. One of the key features of job performance is that it has to be goal-oriented.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

FIG 1: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Shilpa S. & Venkatesha Murthy, (2014) designed the Mysore Tridosha scale and the Mysore Triguna Scale to assess personality from the Ayurvedic perspective. The researchers found 189 basic characteristics traits based on Triguna and Tridosha. These 189 characteristics are part of the 16 Classical Personality types based on the Triguna. Dr. Shilpa Datar (2020) gave a brief of the Personality types and characteristics of different kinds of Prakriti based on Tridosha and Triguna and their importance in psychology from a scientific and academic point of view. Shilpa & Murthy, (2012) have administered the scales to Teachers, IT Professionals, and Police Officers. It was concluded that homogenous groups have similar characteristics.

B.V. et al., (2013) talk about the role of Prakriti in defining one's personality and determining interpersonal relationships. A theoretical framework conceptualized that Prakriti leads to higher organizational performance. Arjun, (2017) studies the correlation between Prakriti and Job Performance. The result showed a positive correlation between Prakriti and the Job performance of the respondents. Khanna et al., (2013) studied the correlation between Trigunas and well-being indicators (PsyCap, Big Five inventory, Satisfaction with life scale, and subjective happiness scale). The results showed a significant correlation between Triguna and well-being indicators, with Sattva guna showing a positive correlation and Rajas and Tamas guna showing a negative correlation with all well-being indicators. Ravindra & Babu, (2021) have studied the relationship between Triguna and emotional well-being (with the indicators being attention, resilience, outlook, social intuition, self-awareness, and sensitivity). They found that Sattva guna and all parameters of emotional well-being have a positive correlation except for resilience showing a negative correlation with Sattva guna and a positive relation with Rajas and Tamas guna. . (Venkatanagarajan & Kamalanabhan, (2019) studied the relationship between PsyCap, Triguna, and Job performance, who conceptualize the formation of PsyCap through the intervention of Triguna, the mediating role of Organization based self-esteem (OBSE), and the moderating role of the supervisor's leadership behavior. Banerjee et al., (2020) have tried to test the impact of Satvik and Rajasik Guna on job performance in the service sector. The study showed no significant relationship between Satvik guna and job performance and a significant relationship between Rajasik guna and job performance.

Luthans & Youssef, (2004) introduced the concept of PsyCap. He talks of positive PsyCap and its impact on the management of an organization. He argues for the need for organizations to move from narrow selection-based techniques towards approaches that help the organization through enhanced performance of the employees with the help of positive PsyCap.

Jung & Yoon, (2015) found a significant relationship between the Positive PsyCap and Job Satisfaction and Job Performance in extension to Job Satisfaction. Abbas & Raja,

(2015) have found a positive relationship between PsyCap and innovativeness in the performance of employees and a negative relationship with job stress. Chen, (2015) found a direct and positive relationship between the PsyCap of leaders and that of their followers which shows that the leader can motivate his employees to exhibit higher positive PsyCap. Durrah et al., (2016) have studied the relationship between positive PsyCap, job satisfaction, and job performance among respondents from Philadelphia University. A significant positive relationship was found between positive PsyCap, job performance, and job satisfaction with job satisfaction acting as a mediator. Gong et al., (2019) have studied the relationship between Emotional intelligence and job performance, with PsyCap as a mediator. The results showed a positive correlation between job performance, EI, and PsyCap, with PsyCap acting as a mediator between the two. NGO & T.T, (2021) have empirically researched the impact of PsyCap on Job performance and Job satisfaction and found a positive impact of PsyCap on Job performance and job satisfaction with it acting as a mediator between PsyCap and job performance. Alessandri et al., (2018) The researchers conceptualize a dynamic mediational model with work engagement as the mediator of the longitudinal relationship between PsyCap and job performance. Witasari & Gustomo, (2020) found a positive relationship between PsyCap, EE, and Job Performance, and EE mediates the relationship between PsyCap and Job Performance. The researchers study the relationship between Human Capital Management Practices (HCMP), Employee engagement, employee performance, and PsyCap. The researchers concluded that HCMP and PsyCap positively impact Employee engagement and HCMP impacts EE and job performance through PsyCap.

4. CONCLUSION

3.1. FIG. 2 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRAKRITI AND PSYCAP

3.2. FIG. 3 IMPACT OF PRAKRITI ON JOB PERFORMANCE

3.3. FIG. 4 IMPACT OF HIGH/ POSITIVE PSYCAP ON JOB PERFORMANCE

The above inferences show a positive relationship

between Prakriti and job performance, through PsyCap.

3.4. FIG. 5 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRAKRITI, PSYCAP, AND JOB PERFORMANCE

The interrelationship between the variables as studied by the researchers through review of literature and inferences drawn from such literature leads the researchers to conclude:

- Prakriti impacts PsyCap
- PsyCap has a positive impact on Job Performance
- Prakriti has a positive relationship with Job Performance
- PsyCap acts as a mediator between Prakriti and Job Performance.

REFERENCES

1. Abbas, M., & Raja, U. (2015). Impact of PsyCap on innovative performance and job stress. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 32(2), 128–138. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cjas.1314>
2. Abstract, S. S., & Venkatesha Murthy, C. G. (2014). Assessment of Traits and Types on Personality: An Indian Psychological Perspective. In *Indian Journal of Psychology*.
3. Alessandri, G., Consiglio, C., Luthans, F., & Borgogni, L. (2018). Testing a dynamic model of the impact of PsyCap on work engagement and job performance. *Career Development International*, 23(1), 33–47. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-11-2016-0210>
4. Arjun, P. P. (2017). *A study of the relationship between Prakriti and the performance of professionals in organizations*. Gujarat Technical University.
5. Banerjee, R., Pathak, R., & Mathur, G. (2020). Relationship between personality and job performance: Indian perspective of Triguna theory. *International Journal of Business Excellence*, 20(1), 122–129. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBEX.2020.104844>
6. B.V., C., Krishna Kishore, K., & Rao, K. N. (2013). Role of Prakriti in Individual Satisfaction and Organizational Performance: An Ayurvedic Perspective. *International Journal on Vedic Foundations of Management*, 123–137.
7. Chen, S. L. (2015). The relationship of leader PsyCap and follower PsyCap, job engagement and job performance: a multilevel mediating perspective. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 26(18), 2349–2365. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2015.1020443>
8. Dr. Shilpa Datar. (2020). Integrated Understanding of Personality Based on Prakriti: Evidence-based Analysis Towards A Wellness Philosophy. *Journal of Psychosocial Research*, 15(2), 447–459.
9. Durrah, O., Alhamoud, A., Alhamoud, A., & Khan, K. (2016). *Positive PsyCap and Job Performance: The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/301549736>
10. Gong, Z., Chen, Y., & Wang, Y. (2019). The Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Job Burnout and Job Performance: Mediating Effect of PsyCap. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02707>
11. Jung, H. S., & Yoon, H. H. (2015). The impact of employees' positive PsyCap on job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behaviors in the hotel. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 27(6), 1135–1156. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-01-2014-0019>
12. Khanna, P., Singh, K., Singla, S., & Verma, V. (2013). Relationship between Triguna theory and well-being indicators. *International Journal of Yoga - Philosophy, Psychology and Parapsychology*, 1(2), 69. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2347-5633.157888>
13. Luthans, F., & Youssef, C. M. (2004). Human, social, and now positive PsyCap management: Investing in people for competitive advantage. *Organizational Dynamics*, 33(2), 143–160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgdyn.2004.01.003>
14. NGO, & T.T. (2021). Impact of PsyCap on job performance and job satisfaction: A case study in Vietnam. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(5), 495–503.
15. Pt. Shastri, K., & Chaturvedi, G. N. (2021). *Charak Samhita Agnivesh* (1986th ed.). Chaukhambha Bharati Academy.
16. Ravindra, P., & Babu, P. (2021). A correlation study between tri-guna and emotional style: A theoretical approach toward developing a working model to integrate tri-guna with affective neuroscience and well-being. *International Journal of Yoga*, 14(3), 213. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijoy.ijoy_52_21

17. Shilpa, S., & Murthy, C. G. V. (2012). Combination of Trigunas in different groups of people. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 38(3), 214–219.
18. Shilpa, S., & Venkatesha Murthy, C. (2011a). Development and standardization of Mysore Tridosha scale. *AYU (An International Quarterly Journal of Research in Ayurveda)*, 32(3), 308. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0974-8520.93905>
19. Shilpa, S., & Venkatesha Murthy, C. (2011b). Understanding personality from Ayurvedic perspective for psychological assessment: A case. *AYU (An International Quarterly Journal of Research in Ayurveda)*, 32(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0974-8520.85716>
20. Trigunas (Sattva, Rajas, Tamas): 3 Gunas to Know Your Personality. (n.d.). In www.fitsri.com. Fitsri.com.
21. Venkatanagarajan, V., & Kamalanabhan, T. J. (2019). Whence, how and when PsyCap enhances job performance: Insights from an east–west conceptual synthesis. *International Journal of Cross Cultural Management*, 19(2), 120–139. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1470595818814553>
22. Witasari, J., & Gustomo, A. (2020). Understanding The Effect of Human Capital Management Practices, PsyCap, and Employee Engagement To Employee Performances. *The Asian Journal of Technology Management (AJTM)*, 13(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.12695/ajtm.2020.13.1.1>